

The Effectiveness of Practical Pedagogic in the High School Face the Challenges and Progressiveness

(A Comparative Analysis of High Schools in Dili East Timor and Malang, East Java)

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Abstract:- The effectiveness of practical pedagogic is hampered by the challenges and caused by the weaknesses of people as the citizenship in the country, the management system and the economic background of the family. *The objective* of this research to identify and discover the effectiveness of practical pedagogic in the schools and their challenges, problematic which hampered in the teaching and learning process in high schools and progressiveness of the effectiveness of practical pedagogic in the high school and it solutions in both Malang East Java and Dili East Timor comparable. The matters of the schools has lots of negative impacts as schools' low students' numbers in each new academic year. The reasons is too many schools for the population, family economic conditions, less attention from the state government to solve the schools risks. *The method* of this research is a qualitative descriptive analysis by observing, interviewing directly with the respondents as primary data, and collecting the additional sources from the link or websites are used as secondary data then presented the result of this research. The writer prepared the questioners verbally directly to the respondents' schools such Sriwedari Junior High School and State public school of Junior high School number 4 of Malang. The respondents were interviewed by the researcher to the school residents in the different ways of investigation, there are 15 numbers of questioners are extended to both respondents, Sriwedari school principal and 9 numbers to public State School number 4 the school principal at different date of interviewed.

I. INTRODUCTION

[1] Pedagogic is another meaning of the art of teaching of the teacher in the high school. It is a science of teaching art the subjects or lesson based curriculum. Pedagogic is the profession of science or theory of teaching. [2] The instruction of the teaching a subject is based on the pedagogical practice. The teacher is a main person who teach and share the knowledge and skills to the students in learning a subject. The quality of instruction is dependent on pedagogy, thus teachers should employ relevant pedagogical strategies in their teaching.

This the part of education which recognized as teaching or training the skill pass to the students as the participants of the learning skills and knowledge. Pedagogical strategies stem from pedagogical theories as defined additionally by Rutto; therefore each and every teacher should be knowledgeable about these theories

It is aimed at equipping teachers with relevant pedagogical knowledge. Means that the teacher with his or her roles as a pedagogic teaching job with the purposes to incentive the capacity knowledge and skills of the learners in the classroom to make change their mind as part of brains storming and be critical thinking.

Education is a versatile (multipurpose) phenomenon, depending on the changes of people's conditions of life. With education the people can have a change their live and achieve an advancement in the society through a family living condition. [3] Poor of rich family it is different economic condition in a living group of people in a public society.

Human weaknesses and gap are changed by the force of the education to achieve what the people call as human intellectualities. When human intellectual abilities reached a certain degree during the initial stage of human development, the behavior of people ceased to be governed just by instincts, and deliberate conduct and actions became more important.

The chances are given to the kids when they enter to be a young girl or a boy the best way for them to enjoy their time with education as a beginner in the basic to high school. This is proven e.g. by education, meaning the care for offspring (children), as a targeted and anticipative activity. To acquire a new knowledge and skill as the beginners of study in the school.

Timor Leste and Indonesia are a neighborhood country the living condition of the economic background of people almost similar with each other. The people of both countries dependent each other as same as step father even today. [4] All the educational activities and teaching movement are similar, however the government of Indonesia has left East Timor after 24 years the education systems based curriculum are commonly used by all education institutions in East Timor as known Timor-Leste today.

Dili is a capital city of Timor-Leste with the total population [5] ± 324,269 people. And the total population are 1.34 million people who reside in the land of Timor which is today as a former land was colonized by Portuguese Timor for 450 years (4 ½ century) [6] (Silva, 2018). but progress of the educational situation in the country, and just force the people become Portuguese slaver to work as auxiliary (to help the government for work without pay, buy for the taxes only).

[7] Malang is a regency part of Province of East Java. It has total population totally ± 847,182 people in the middle of 2023. Majority of Javanese, followed by Madurese and Chinese generations according to Wiki foundation.

II. DEFINITION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PEDAGOGY

An effective teacher is able to provide a good opportunity for students to take part in flexible groups that collaborate a significant task, and answer to questions that to support an achievement of learning goals. Pedagogy is “the art, science, or profession of teaching. [8] They instead direct the reader to texts like pedagogy of the oppressed or to teaching models such as “brain-based,” “critical,” or “culturally responsive pedagogy.”

The examples of works are effective in demonstrating what success looks like, and how to achieve success. This reduces cognitive load. [9] And give clear examples defining, providing the meaning of the subject or lessons, the content of the subject must be clearly understandable then make some evaluation and assessment.

[10] The effectiveness of a teacher is a part of his or her maximum preparation, give clear explanation, giving clear definition, clear defining the meaning and well understanding, well clarification. ‘Effective’ is producing a desire or intended result.

Effectiveness is derived from a single word ‘effective’ morphologically suffixed with ‘ness’. The term effective generally refers to something that produces a desired outcome or achieves a specific goal. The basic word of ‘effect’ means a change which is a result or consequence of an action or other cause. An impression produced in a person’s mind.

The effectiveness of pedagogical practice means the art of practical teaching then do evaluation and assessment to the students in learning the skills and knowledge they obtain from the teacher. A teacher can teach professional way to the pupil in learning the subjects from the curriculum lists.

In teaching, also referred to as pedagogy, a knowledgeable individual facilitates learning by altering its behavior in the presence of a naïve observer. The process of pedagogic teaching is the effort of the increasing of the students’ skill in learning the subject taught by the teacher. A teacher much more adequate professional skills before teach the learners in the classroom schools.

The use of the term "andragogy" to mean education of *adults* and the term "pedagogy" to mean education of children is etymologically inaccurate. Although pedagogy derives from "pais," meaning *child*, from antiquity pedagogy also has stood for education in general--without reference to learners' ages. [11] Malcolm Knowles andragogy is the teaching arts to the adult education process. The education is provided to the adult people, such as the students of higher academic institutions. Hence the education referred to adult people called andragogy derives from "aner," meaning *adult male* and not *adult* of *either sex*. Given current efforts to purge English of sexist words, introduction of a term that excludes women is nonsensical.

According [12] Khumar Shah and Sanothimi the Greek word for child (usually a boy) is pais (the stem of this is paid), and leader is agogus-so a paidagogus or pedagogue was literally a leader of children. [13] Pedagogic in this case referred to lead the child. The slaves who were arrested by the king to take care the boy but not the girl because the girl was forbidden. The king’s boys to be trained such as gymnastic, poetry, sing the songs, martial arts and so on.

[14] The word ‘pedagogy’ by pointing out that it derives from the Greek paidag gos, which is formed from pais (‘boy’, ‘girl’, ‘child’) and agein (‘to lead’, ‘to bring’). Hence, the conclusion is usually drawn that the paidag gos led his charge to school.

Teaching is widespread amongst humans according to the teaching experiences (hereafter, the “Natural Pedagogy” or “NP” hypothesis), human teaching relies on dedicated mechanisms that evolved for the purpose of social transmission and are unique to our species.

The method or techniques that a teacher uses for having his or her job as a teacher to continue running the activities as a teacher such as design the subject, preparing the lesson plan, reading and comprehensible the contents of the subject designed and explain and re-explaining.

Comprehensive theory of teaching or practical pedagogy will benefit from integrating perspectives and empirical phenomena from evolutionary and developmental disciplines. To affect the pupils in engaging the learning subjects as science of life in their living society of humanism as a part social environment. Society is our part of living blending for changing by using skills and knowledge for achieving the future. One possibility is that children’s ability to learn efficiently in social contexts, and from teaching specifically, is itself learned over the first few years of life.

In the early 1970s during the era of Malcolm Knowles when andragogy and the concept was about the adult education, that adults learners and children learn do not same was firstly introduced in the United States of America by Malcolm Knowles, the idea was groundbreaking and sparked much subsequent research and controversy at that time.

III. EDUCATION, CONCEPT AND THEORY OF EDUCATION

Education is similar with the teaching and pedagogy learning. [15] It referred to gaining the skills and knowledge from a teacher or giving the training to the pupils or students in the school classrooms. Education from the basic word to 'educate' to teach or to train.

Education according to Dr. Jasvir Kaur [16] the process of learning easy and effective like Known to unknown, Simple to complex, Concrete to abstract, Particular to general, Deductive to inductive, Psychological to logical, Empirical to rational, Indefinite to definite. We can use them in accumulation or as a personal approach depending upon the content, age and grade and level of students. According to Kaur argues that there are three different words in Latin about the term of 'education' etymologically as in Latin 'educare' to bring up, 'to nourish' and to 'raise'; and 'educere' implies, 'to draw out', to lead out; and while 'educatum' means "the act of teaching or training."

Education means nourish the good qualities in individual and draw out the best in every individual. Education seeks to develop the innate inner capacities of individual. Pedagogy is science of instructions and to lead the students. As some additional definitions from the Sanskrit 'Shiksha' derived from the word 'shas', means to discipline, to control, to instruct or to teach. And the word 'vidya' derived from 'vid' means 'to know'. Mahatma Gandhi argues that "by education, I mean an all-round drawing out of the best in child and man-body, mind and spirit."

➤ According to Kaur, there are Two Types of Education Meaning, Narrower Meaning and Broader Meaning:

- In the narrow sense, education is limited or inadequate to school and university instruction. Education begins when a child enters the institution and ends when he and she leaves after completing a particular course of study. Under this arrangement, education of the child is over when, having received the given amount of knowledge, he or she leaves the institution and takes up some occupation in life. The success of the education of the child is evaluated in terms of passing the examination. That person who is not involved in this type of education as Kaur defines it, they are labeled as illiterate persons.

In its narrow sense, Education means Schooling. Here, everything is systematic, prefix and predetermined. The curriculum, methods of teaching, examination and teacher are prefix and predetermined. It is a systematic process to achieve the definite goals of education through classroom instruction.

- In a broad sense, this type of education is not confined to any institution. It is a life-long process. It begins with the mother's womb and ends in the tomb. In every phase of life, the individual learns the education or gains the knowledge directly or indirectly. In its broader meaning, education is a life-long process. In this connection, J.S. Mackenzie says: In the wider sense, "it is a process that

goes on throughout life, and is promoted by every experience in life." According to Prof. Dnmvile, "Education includes all the influences which act upon an individual during his passage from the cradle to the grave."

Education is a skill capacity from a skill man to an unskilled person to wake him or her up from unknowledgeable capacity. Example a skilled person is a person who has gained previous knowledge then with his or her effort to facilitate and teach for affecting the skills and knowledge that he had got. The capacity knowledge from someone to make a person singularly and two persons or more plurality to have something new to know.

There are Brown in his book with its title *Human Teaching for Human Learning* defines that there are three types of education or teaching methods, they are:

- **Confluent** education is the term for the integration or following together of the *affective* and *cognitive* elements in individual group learning, sometimes called humanistic or psychological education. The term "confluent" generally means flowing together or merging.
- **Affective** refers to the feeling or emotional aspect of experience and learning. How a child or adult feels about wanting to learn, how he feels as he learns, and what he feels after he has learned are included in the affective domain. The term "affective" relates to emotions and feelings. It encompasses various aspects of emotional experience and expression.
- **Cognitive** refers to the activity of the mind in knowing an object to intellectual functioning. The term "cognitive" relates to mental processes such as perception, memory, judgment, and reasoning. It encompasses how we acquire knowledge and understanding through thought, experience, and the senses.

What an individual learns and the intellectual process of learning it would fall within the cognitive domain – unless what is learned is an attitude or value, which would be affective learning. Cognitive learning is an accepting the subject taught would be understandable and be benefit for the participant. The mental action or process of acquiring knowledge through thought, experience, and the senses. Affective means 'influence' learning with the sentiment of emotional. Confluent is consistent, convergence.

[17] It consists of the facts observed, recalled, read, and talked concern and the thoughts suggested in course of a development of a situation having an objective. These facts need to be purified more specific in relevant with the subjects of school instruction, the learning which make the curriculum according to John Dewey. What is the significance of our definition in application related to writing, mathematics, history, nature study, drawing, singing, physics, chemistry, modern and foreign languages, and so on?

Teacher or a teacher is a person who gives an instruction and run his or her education to train and influence his/her participants who wishes to hear and listen for. Teacher is a person who teaches in a school.

In its narrow sense, Education means Schooling. Here, everything is systematic, prefix and predetermined. The curriculum, methods of teaching, examination and teacher are prefix and predetermined. It is a systematic process to achieve the definite goals of education through classroom instruction.

➤ *Analytical Meaning of Education*

- Education is a process
- Education is bi-polar process

Fig 1: [16] “Indian Concept of Education.”

Education has three pillars, they are [i] teacher: the red color ball for teacher means shows a teacher prepares the subject, hard works, get small wage each month. Education referred to someone who had acquired knowledge and skills in the previous time then gain the position in the government seats. Teachers and the government entities can make change the curriculum or subjects. Without a teacher no one can teach a subject. Because experience and knowledge only built from other person as [18] John Locke extends his theory of *Tabularasa* (1632-1704). [ii] Curriculum: Curriculum is green color because it make people always in green obtain the knowledge and skills in learning the sciences then get a nice job to make people in progressive family. Without curriculum there is zero education. [19] Conceptually, curriculum is viewed as a construct, a verbalization of an extremely complex idea or a set of ideas. [iii] Pupil or students: There is no education if without the students who are going to make advance for their capacity knowledge. Students learn much more and more from the curriculum prepared by the teacher as a trainer person.

Fig 2: This Graphic is Designed by the Writer Based on the Comprehension of Himself

When a person read and learn a subject or some simple things like booklet, newspaper, magazines and so on because he or she knows and familiar with a language can understand the content of sources. Language is an essential factor to obtain and reach an understanding of something with a proficiency of a language.

[20] Vygotsky points out that as a result, Bruner calls this innate system the language assistance system (LAS), whose primary function is to ensure ‘the ordered pattern of transfer of initiative in communication from the adult to the child’ The transferences of the science and potential knowledge is through a language. Language is a main factor to have skill in language ability. According to Vygotsky there are two things, physical objective and psychological objective. Physical objective concerning the physical health. And psychological concept about the language ability. The language is an essential part to learn a subject through language ability of the students.

Vygotsky emphasized the importance of ‘mediated activity’ in the development of higher psychological functions. He identified both physical tools and psychological tools as mediational means. However, for Vygotsky, psychological tools, particularly language, were of primary concern.

[21] *Constructivist learning theory meaning is seen as a cognitive activity that produces mental models that represent perceptions of reality*”. CLT (Constructivist Learning Theory) objectively used to identify how to undergo the learning procedures in the classroom, and how knowledge is produced In the other hand, to understand the concept of Collaborative Learning Environment (CLE), it is a scheme priory developed to assist the **participation, collaboration,** and **cooperation** of users sharing a common goal....

➤ *The Challenges of the both Dili Timor-Leste and Malang High Schools*

• *Dili, Timor-Leste*

[22] Dili is a capital city of República Democrática de Timor-Leste (RDTL) it was recognized since the Portuguese colonial periods as called Cidade de Provincia de Ultramarino of Timor Portuguese. Ultramarino means a land of overseas. It was formed by the Portuguese since 11 of August 1769 after Oecusse Enclave attacked by the Topaz forces. It was established by the Portuguese and the Dominican Friar. The reasons of the Dili was transferred to Dili, in 1769 because of frequent attack by the topazes forces during Dutch King Francisco Hornay III and another reason is for doing the commercial activities on selling and buy sandalwood, wax or honeybees between Timorese and Malay, China etc.

It has ± **324.269** people according to the population census 2022 and the entire population over the territory **1,384,286** as of 2023 according to the census, 2023. From these total populations are mostly farmers as farm workers such food plantation, animal husbandry, businessmen, fishermen. They are depended of the result of their working hard to support their children sent into the schools.

[23] There state private kindergarten are 14 schools and private or Catholic kindergarten schools are 12 schools; the 43 state primary schools and 16 private primary schools; Basic school grade 1 to 9 years are 14 public schools and 8 private schools; 43 public pre-secondary or junior high schools and 16 private junior high schools; Secondary public or state schools are 11 and private secondary schools are 10.

➤ *The Total Schools in Timor-Leste in Whole Territory at Least:*

- Kindergarten are 1520; 89 Government kindergarten schools and 53 Catholic or private kindergarten schools.
- Basic / primary schools are: grade 1 to 9 are: 207 government school and 50 private schools;
- Basic / elementary school 1 to 6 years: 564 government schools and 103 private or Catholic schools;
- Basic /junior high schools are: 335 state or government schools and 25 private schools;
- General Secondary high schools are: public or state secondary high schools are 44 and private or Catholic secondary high schools are 29;
- Ensino Técnico Vocational or Technical Vocational high schools are: 20 government schools and 1 private school.

• *Challenges*

Some challenges faced by the some schools, the lack of teaching staff and most of the teaching staff are going to tertiary ages and to be retired soon. Most of school building conditions are poor and serious condition, and there is no internet or link of *wifi* or *wireless* internet. The students less intention to read the books in the library because hampered by unskilled language. Timor-Leste has adopted Portuguese as official language it is hard for them to read the books, and Bahasa Indonesia is difficult to them to understand. The

young generation who was born above 2000 they don't understand to speak Bahasa Indonesia. The government of Timor-Leste pay prior attention on this matter to be fixed. The young teachers who are volunteer teaching in many years are being stopped by the Minister of Education in 2023. And everything in running implementation in each schools in the district cooperate together with the chief of regional education ministry and school entities.

[24] The Minister has stopped the contract teachers based on the decree law (*Dekretu-Lei, nº. 31/2023 de 31 de Maio, artigu 11" kona-ba ingresu espesial*). The total of contract teachers are **1,499** and many of them has double jobs beside a teacher as teaching staff in an education institution and some are not eligible to be a teacher. The total numbers of **1,388** would be called back to participate the examination test through legal recruitment also to be permanent government teaching staff in the future.

[25] The private school are minimal attention by the Ministry of education. Because they have own money to establish a school in the community area. For this reason the private schools are paid attention by the foundation of the Catholic Church or private no-Catholic schools. Also the lack of the entrance new phase of students' enrolment each year in the whole territory of country. All the facilities are provided by the private school institutions and the foundation in this case the Catholic Church and the school founders in the districts. Some private schools are not responsible by the Catholic church for example they are created by the group of people who are in the foundation organization such as Dili International schools, Fundasaun Cristal or Instituto Superior Cristal (ISC) has schools started from kindergarten, elementary, pre-secondary, secondary school until University.

The capacity of the students are overflow every year in each school from the government schools and including the private schools or Catholic schools or none Catholic schools, even pay much money every month. There are two private category schools in East Timor, Catholic private schools are built by the Catholic Church from priests and sisters congregations. And the non-Catholic private school are built by the private foundation which has a group of people to have initiative to build the schools that has an intention and willingness to build the schools; also some International schools are built by the International Philippine situated in Dili and established by the Philippine teachers under the agreement of the Ministry of Education. The government has paid lots of money to the Portuguese foreign teachers but no one can speak good Portuguese in the classroom teaching subject as the government force the teachers and students to communicate easy Portuguese.

The generation are forcedly to learn Portuguese language therefore the government of Timor-Leste has recruited thousands of Portuguese teachers to teach Portuguese language since 2000 but resulted many participants do not know how to speak well Portuguese. Very often the teachers who are teaching Portuguese language courses do not use translation methods and use single

Portuguese language only, and for this effort the government of Timor-Leste expensed lots of money for paying the Portuguese foreign teachers.

The weaknesses of the government of Timor-Leste in solving this matter to profound learning Portuguese must be involve the native into the program and should be fallen to the native Timorese giving the opportunity for capacity building in learning Portuguese language outside the country then teach the young people it is full benefit to help the people in understanding and comprehending the contents of the language easily because teaching a language must use also translation method language 2 and language 1 (L2 to L1). The government created the program limited fund to their own native east Timorese to learn more Portuguese and many other languages outside the country, very often the government provides the fund to the Timorese for competing the scholarship and when scholarship participants has finished their study in abroad there is no job vacancies for them after return to their homeland, however, the participants also nominated by the government entities must apply job vacancy is being provided many time the participants do not pass from the application test inside. It caused by the nepotism and collusion matters in the internal part of the institution.

- *The progressive*

The central government through Ministry of Education together with regional leaders of regional education and local school institutions are highly cooperative to control, supervise and monitoring the schools, school principal, teachers and students in the district areas every year. The government through Ministry of education, provide the fundraising twice in a year to repair the building of schools, additional school facilities like chairs, book references. Some of the teaching staff are recruited to go to abroad for capacity building enhancement in some foreign countries as a program called *programa intercambio*. The government cooperatively with UNICEF has been establishing the program of *Merenda Escolar*, provide food to feed the all basic schools in the whole territory of the state, from kindergarten until elementary schools.

Portuguese is adopted as an official language beside Tetun is utilized as a national language in the whole territory in the country it consecrated in the Constitution of the República Democrática de Timor-Leste (it briefed as RDTL) in the recent time during 450 years of Portuguese occupation in the island of former Timor Portuguese during its era.

Fig 3: Sra. Luisa is doing her Practical Pedagogic Activity in the Classroom to the Students of Ensino Básico Central 3^o Ciclo de Akadiruhun, Dili..

<https://www.moe.gov.tl/index.php/sistema-educacao/ensino-basico>

- *Effective Practical Pedagogic in the Class*

[31] As Indonesia's rules in practical teaching or pedagogical effectiveness uses the technique or method that the teachers use are: lesson plan designing before a teacher goes to teach a subject specifically which is called: Specific Instructional Objective (Tujuan Instruksi Khusus – TIK) it is a method which the teacher usually use to teach the students in the classroom. To design and formatted into a specific model to make the students easily and clearly understand all the contents of the subjects of the problem statement, skills or knowledge, and the competent of the attitude will be reached by the learners in preparing or designing the subject before begin for teaching.

The benefit of specific instructional objective is to determine or control the objective of teaching and learning process and the determining the initial standard instructional, preparing instructional design, forming the item test instruments, learning evaluation, make the reviewing the activities of the learning and also select the learning media in learning processes. Need to be defined that the criteria which existed when a student will do a task based on the specific instructional objective.

[32] The General Instruction Objective (Tjuan Instruksi Umum or TIU) it is the teaching models is generally used by the teachers started from basic school to higher schools, the subject designed are effectively teaching the learners in professional way. It is called in English as 'lesson plan'. Before a teaching having the class tomorrow, today or today a teacher must prepare the subject and reading or writing all the contents of the subject itself. The objective is easy to a teacher before he or she is going to start to teach a lesson. These techniques are used by the Timorese until recent time as same as Indonesia education Institution all around the territory of Indonesia.

The education system in East Timor just continue the former education system left by Indonesia after 24 years in the country. However, East Timor is adopting European Curriculum Transfer accumulation system (ECTS) blended it with Indonesia curriculum so far from the elementary school to higher educational Institutions.

➤ *Malang Schools*

Malang is a town of regency part of East Java province in Indonesia it is a place for technological learning and research center. It was a kingdom town ruled by some kings 1000BC such as Singhasari King and Gajayana king according to pre-history and Malang was occupied by the Dutch colonial since 1767s. Malang is historical place of the kings' confrontation since the fallen of the Majapahit Kingdoms then Gajah Mada king escaped into Malang city.

[26] As it is mentioned above that Malang population 847,182 and the junior high school has 5082 for East Java and the secondary schools has 1.517.and elementary schools are 19.003 according to the data of Education Ministry (2024). And the kindergarten are 18.822 schools in east Java only. The population of Java are highest than other places in Indonesia.

Fig 4: SMP Negeri 4 Malang is a Junior High School (State Public School Number 4 Malang). The Students are being Taught the Computer Practical Activity in the Classroom. Photo: detik.com 2024.

Table 1: The list of Total Schools in East Java, Indonesia According to the List of Ministry of Education Indonesia for 2024.

Total Population of Malang Regency in sub district administration	Schools in East Java			
	Kindergarten	Elementary	Pre-secondary school	Secondary Schools
847,182	18.822	19.003	5082	1.517
Malang Schools 	363 school unit [27] Widiyanto, 2023.	195 state School units and are private elementary 92 schools units. + SLB deficient extreme School 2 units public schools, and 12 private school units.	30 public Junior high schools; private junior high schools Units are 87	11 state public schools; private Secondary schools, and state senior high schools are 37 + Vocational high schools are: state public schools are 13 Units, and private schools are 39 units.

IV. CHALLENGES OF EDUCATION SYSTEM OF INDONESIA

Most of the must less the students each year mainly the private schools. Some of Medias has revealed out about the schools problematic and lack of students everywhere in the towns or in the villages. For example a district of East Java province has lots of matters concern the minimal students in participating into the school each year. It impacted by the family economic background and most of the students' family are from unemployment. The family send their children to the state public schools but normally the students are overflow more the standard criteria that the school need and this can cause rests of the students have to go to private school.

The writer interviewed a principal of a junior high school called SMP (Sekolah Menengah Pertama) Sriwedari part of Penanggungan village and Klojen sub district at Bogor street no. 1 on April 4th 2024, he explained that each new students enrollment at his school just accept less than 10 new students every year. The principal of Sriwedari, Mr. Rudiyanto, S.Pd., points out that most of the private schools

face serious matters in engaging the study activities and similar problem happen to other school too. The writer has approached the principal of the school for interviewing during 45 minutes. The principal added that only 15 permanent or fulltime teachers and other non-permanent teaching staff including other additional teaching staff from other schools.

The researcher also asked him about the school must be closed because less students more than normal condition, he responds that the “government refuses to closed even though the school has faced serious problem. Beside that the writer also ask him about this school to hand over to the government to become public state school but the founder of Sriwedari refuses it. All the teaching staff needs are paid attention by the government each year providing the fundraised as subsidies to the private schools twice in a year. All school library references are updated by the central and regional educational leaders.

In Malang regency with its wide and large area has a lot of elementary and junior high schools. There are 491 schools according to Wicana (Wicana, 2023) in the article of Jawa Post media there was no new students enrolled in the new academic year. This case has occurred in three places in Malang area. According to the local and regional government of Malang states that 491 primary and junior high schools no new students to register into the schools mainly the private schools.

The writer directly came approached to a state public school named SMP Negeri (Government Junior High school number 4 of Malang) also interviewed with a lady school principal Dr. Pancapriyana Dinihari, M.Pd. According to her, the school that she leads has a high quality prior in the national competition usually to get top scores and gets many premium from the central government. The premium on the national traditional cultural event in the central parts government. Her students from first to third grade are totally 870 students also has 15 fulltime teachers.

She adds that all the school necessity are complete. Because the school is government property. If any recruitment is done it is provided by the regional government through online recruitment. After examination result then share the new teachers to each school based on the how many teachers will be needed in each public state schools based on their need and avoid also the teacher not to get the double job at other institutions.

The head of regional education of Wonogiri regency, Mr. Gino efforts to grouping the schools but the head of regency of Wonogiri rejected it because everything are decided by the community who live at the area. Sometimes the community wants their children go to school closer with the main roads but they don't like schools that nearby with their house yard.

[30] There are 99 elementary schools has no new students in Semarang, Central Java province in the initial months of January, 2024, according J.C. Tukiman Taruna of media Kompas (Taruna, 2023). Some places which state public schools existed but no students because of quality of the schools are high at the private schools parts, while some other places has no students at private schools and the state public schools are highest students because of the family living conditions are mostly high risks of economic problem.

➤ *Progressiveness*

The schools are needed to open continuity and the government pay attention to all private schools by raising fund as subsidized twice every year by central and regional government.

V. RESULT AND FINDING

The finding in this research on the effectiveness comparable both, Malang and Dili East Timor are almost similar. But some serious problematic occurred are in Malang regency has low students in many schools including in some parts of other regencies. In Dili and entirely all territories of

East Timor mostly basic schools has high numbers of students at every schools each year. The reason is new state was born need the human resources. The limited numbers of schools in each sub district. But in Malang has overflow of schools and can cause the limited numbers of students.

Some parts are the students want the state public school because the state schools are free and most of the families are from high risks economic matter. Some other reasons are from the state schools are low quality if comparable with the private schools in Indonesia with Malang schools.

In East Timor the state schools are free and private schools are paid each month and less paid attention by the government entities in this case the regional head of education and the national government in the central. The students are overflow each schools even the private schools.

The effectiveness of teaching in the school classroom use the same teaching *methods* and *techniques* because the education system in Timor-Leste left by the Indonesia education system after 1999 referendum. The teaching subjects in the classroom pedagogic use mix curriculums in the recent time, Indonesian curriculum and European curriculum called European Curriculum Transfer Accumulation system (ECTS) in the basic schools (Quinn, 2023). The teachers use the Specific Instructional objective (SIO/TIK) and General Instructional Objective (GIO/TIU) in both Timor-Leste's teachers and Malang Indonesia's teachers.

VI. METHODS

This method of research is a qualitative descriptive analysis method by using technique observation, interview, and share the questioners to 2 respondents, the principal school of Sriwedari Junior High school 15 numbers and the principal school of state public Junior High School number 4 of Malang, 9 numbers. The questioners are written in Bahasa Indonesia for both respondents. And turnitin plagiarism checker is done for avoiding the plagiarism aspect before presented this article into the publication.

VII. DISCUSSION

Education is the main factor and principle of human life for promoting and developing their own life in the family also the state as to treat and manage the development of the whole state through a good human resources. Through education people can have change the progressiveness of the state through powerful of innovative learning can make development and advancement in a country in discovery and new philosophical scientific conceptual of the human resources itself. The government members are created and resulted from education. They are from teachers of teachers. Teachers are the teachers of professors' professors.

Talcott Parsons (Hoy and Forsyth, *ibid*, 1982:4) argues that the technical function of schools is a teaching process that is "*Teaching process, and an entire subsystems revolves around the problems associated with effective teaching and*

learning. Skilled professionals-teachers-are directly responsible for the teaching-learning process in the schools. The technical level is the managerial, whose prime concern is the integration of organizational activities."

VIII. RECOMMENDATION

Teacher must be paid especial attention to their live because teachers are the key concepts of the development of the state. Teachers are the discovery of the development of the state. They are professors before other professors are born. Their knowledge and skills are the gate and bridge of the state. They are born to born the professor in a country with the high dedication in risk and suffer in front of men *they are a hero without merit*. No government without them, no professor without them.

- The teachers must paid especial attention to their monthly wage by the government.
- The students which are from the family high risks economic background should be subsidized by the state government.
- The poverty's children must be free of study in every school institution. They are poor because of misery of war and conflict.
- All the private or state companies or rich people must provide the fund to the poor people. Please raise them up from their suffering and down dignities. An Indonesian proverb says, "*Stand the same, low sit the same, heavy can be carried on the head and light the same put on the shoulders.*"

CONCLUSION

Some parts of this conclusion that mostly Indonesia schools are various problematic in the high school institutions but the regional entities effort to solve it then no solutions so far mainly the lack of new students in every new academic year each year. The reasons is too many schools everywhere in Java. In Dili East Timor schools has serious risks in the building conditions, most teachers are entry to elderly ages. The young contracted teachers are being stopped by the Ministry of education with the reasons just to re-update the management system to the contracted teachers. The new students are overflow every year including the private schools. The systematic practical pedagogy are similar or almost same both East Timor and Indonesia use similar method of teaching, Specific Instructional Objective (SIO) and General Instructional Objective (GIO) before starting the practical pedagogic in the classroom. East Timor two mix curriculum, European Curriculum Transfer Accumulation System (ECTS) and Indonesia Curriculum. The Ministry of Education Indonesia and Timor-Leste are doing the similar job such as provide the fundraise to the school twice in a years as same as monitoring and supervising to each public schools.

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